

WAYS OF INTERSTATE COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION OF THE MEMBER STATES OF THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION

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Abstract. *The document explores mechanisms and ways of interstate cooperation among the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in the fields of science and innovation. Key focuses include joint research programs, development of innovation infrastructure, protection of intellectual property, and academic mobility. It also highlights successful projects in artificial intelligence, renewable energy, climate research, and the creation of startup and high-tech zones.*

Keywords: *SCO, science, innovation, interstate cooperation, artificial intelligence, renewable energy, technology zones, startups, intellectual property, academic mobility.*

The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) is a regional international organization that unites a number of Eurasian states. One of the key objectives of the SCO is to develop cooperation between member states in various fields, including science and innovation. Given global challenges such as digital transformation, technological modernization and sustainable development, scientific and technical cooperation plays a vital role for the SCO countries.

One of the most important areas of cooperation is the creation of joint research programs. These programs may include:

- Development of new technologies in energy, information technology, biotechnology and other priority areas.
- Unification of research centers and universities to implement common projects.
- Joint scientific research within the framework of initiatives aimed at combating global challenges such as climate change, healthcare and food security.

In 2023, the SCO countries supported more than 200 joint scientific projects, including research in such areas as artificial intelligence and renewable energy. Russia and China, for example, plan to implement at least 10 major projects by 2025. These countries are actively developing joint research in the field of artificial intelligence and big data processing. The University of Artificial Intelligence in Moscow, together with Chinese colleagues, is developing new machine learning algorithms, which facilitates the exchange of knowledge and technology between the countries. Kazakhstan and Russia are also working on research in the field of renewable energy sources, creating joint scientific laboratories to develop solar and wind power plant technologies.

Over the past five years, the SCO countries have invested heavily in the development of innovation zones, including the creation of more than 50 technology parks and incubators. For example, Kazakhstan and China are actively cooperating in the creation of modern technology zones to support startups and research.

The development of innovation infrastructure is another tool for cooperation, which includes:

- Joint investment in the creation of high-tech zones and innovation clusters.
- Exchange of experience and technology transfer between SCO member states.
- Development of international centers to support startups and scientific and technical projects.

A number of countries have already done some work in this area. For example, Kazakhstan and China have launched a project to create an international technology park in Astana, the purpose of which is to develop startups in the field of technology and innovation. The technology park will support scientific research in areas such as nanotechnology and bioengineering.

In order for cooperation in science and innovation between the SCO countries to be effective, it is necessary to ensure the harmonization of legal frameworks and standards. Important steps here are:

- Developing common regulatory documents governing activities in the field of science and technology.
- Harmonizing standards for the protection of intellectual property and scientific patents.
- Establishing legal mechanisms to facilitate the cross-border movement of researchers and equipment.

In 2021, the SCO countries developed uniform rules for the protection of intellectual property, including patent law and trademarks. This agreement helps scientists and developers in the participating countries protect their inventions at the international level. The SCO also has a program to unify scientific standards and requirements for research in the field of biotechnology. This facilitates cross-border collaboration and allows scientists from different countries to jointly develop medical drugs and treatments.

In the framework of the SCO agreements on the protection of intellectual property, more than 150 patents related to joint scientific developments were filed in 2022. This facilitates cross-border cooperation and protects innovations at the international level.

A vital component of scientific cooperation is the educational sphere. To develop scientific potential, it is necessary to:

- Create academic mobility programs that allow students and scientists from the SCO countries to exchange knowledge and experience.
- Develop joint educational programs in the field of high technology, engineering, and natural sciences.
- Conduct summer schools, advanced training courses and master classes with the participation of leading scientists and specialists from the SCO countries.

Every year, more than 10,000 students from the SCO countries participate in exchange programs. Universities from Russia, China, India and Uzbekistan are already participating in the academic mobility program, which allows students to conduct research in the leading scientific centers of the SCO countries. For example, students from Uzbekistan can study at the best Chinese universities in the fields of high technology. Russian and Indian universities offer joint master's programs in engineering and technology. Students can study in either India or Russia, receiving degrees from both countries.

Kazakhstan, Russia, and China are collaborating on environmental programs aimed at studying climate change and developing green technologies. One of the projects is the creation of a system for monitoring the state of the environment in Central Asia using satellite data.

The examples provided illustrate real achievements in interstate cooperation in science and innovation among SCO member states. They highlight the importance of coordinating efforts to achieve common goals in scientific and technological progress, which helps to address global challenges and develop an innovative economy in the region.

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